

Red & Near-Infrared Light as an Environmental Determinant of Cellular and Systemic Health

Biological Mechanisms, Dose Metrics, and Regulatory Implications

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Executive Summary

This white paper advocates for a critical re-evaluation of the systemic health benefits of red and near-infrared (NIR) light in human biology. This white paper proposes that red and NIR light be considered an environmental health factor, analogous to other regulated biological inputs such as nutrition, physical activity and air quality. We recommend commissioning a formal scoping review to assess light exposure as a determinant of cellular and systemic health, identify biologically relevant exposure ranges, and evaluate whether these findings warrant integration into environmental health guidance and public-health research priorities.

Red and NIR light are biologically active components of the electromagnetic spectrum that interact with human tissues at non-thermal intensities. A growing body of mechanistic and experimental evidence demonstrates that NIR light influences mitochondrial energy metabolism, nitric oxide signaling, redox balance, intracellular melatonin synthesis, inflammation, pain, tissue repair and neural function (Son et al., 2025).

Despite this evidence demonstrated across cellular, animal and clinical models, optical radiation is currently regulated exclusively through a hazard-prevention framework focused on acute tissue injury from thermal damage. However infrared photons should not be regarded solely as heat photons. In the near-infrared (NIR) range (approximately 700–1100nm), photon–tissue interactions are predominantly non-thermal when delivered at low irradiances, enabling photochemical and photobiological effects. In contrast, mid and far infrared wavelengths are more strongly absorbed by water and biological tissues, resulting in a predominance of thermal effects. Photobiomodulation (PBM) therefore selectively employs red and near-infrared wavelengths, as they are capable of penetrating biological tissue and eliciting cellular and mitochondrial responses, such as modulation of cytochrome c oxidase activity, without inducing significant tissue heating.

No complementary framework exists to evaluate whether chronic underexposure to biologically relevant wavelengths of infrared light may impair mitochondrial function and long-term health. A hypothesis that remains largely untested at the population level.

This document highlights an emerging area of biological science with potential relevance to public health. Considering the growing body of accumulating mechanistic and experimental evidence, it proposes that red and NIR light exposure warrants systematic evaluation within future research and public-health frameworks. To this end, commissioning a formal scoping review of red and NIR light exposure with associated biological and health outcomes is recommended, to assess the strength of evidence, identify key knowledge gaps and inform subsequent public health guidelines.

1. Definitions and Scope

The electromagnetic (EM) spectrum encompasses all types of electromagnetic radiation. It ranges from short wavelengths with high energy to long wavelengths with low energy. The spectrum includes gamma rays, X-rays, ultraviolet (UV) radiation, visible light, infrared (IR) radiation, microwaves, and radio waves. IR radiation occupies the region between visible light and microwave radiation, beginning just beyond the red edge of the visible spectrum. While the conventional boundary is cited at approximately 700nm, typical human vision in practice extends only to around 720–730nm, with the 700–780nm region often designated as 'far-red' [citation]. IR extends to approximately 1 millimetre (mm) in wavelength (Stockman & Sharpe, 2000).

Photobiomodulation, previously referred to as low level laser therapy (LLLT), describes the modulation of cellular function through exposure to defined wavelengths of light that elicit photobiological responses. The PBM spectrum encompasses both red (600–700nm) and near-infrared (700–1100nm) wavelengths, which are commonly applied in combination due to their interactions with mitochondrial chromophores (Hamblin & Demidova, 2006). The primary focus of this paper will be on near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths due to their capacity to penetrate biological tissues and induce measurable physiological effects (Karu, 1999; Hamblin, 2018). NIR light stimulates photobiological activity at non-thermal irradiances. This distinction is supported by defined action spectra demonstrating wavelength-specific cellular responses to NIR exposure, differentiating photobiomodulatory effects from purely heat-mediated mechanisms (Karu & Kolyakov, 2005). NIR wavelengths exhibit lower absorption and scattering in biological tissues compared with visible light, enabling deeper tissue penetration; this has been characterised across multiple tissue types through measurement of wavelength-dependent optical properties (Jacques, 2013).

Humans are continuously exposed to low-intensity infrared (IR) and near-infrared (NIR) radiation from environmental sources, including solar radiation. This background exposure occurs at irradiances several orders of magnitude lower than those typically applied in clinical PBM protocols. While environmental IR exposure is not delivered in a controlled or targeted manner, it nonetheless represents a persistent biological stimulus that may contribute to basal photobiological signaling processes over long timescales. Importantly, while PBM findings cannot be directly extrapolated to environmental exposure scenarios, they establish dose-response relationships, mechanistic pathways, and safety thresholds that inform translational hypotheses. Clinical PBM research provides a critical mechanistic framework for understanding how optical radiation interacts with biological tissues. Controlled PBM studies allow precise manipulation of wavelength, irradiance, fluence, and exposure timing, enabling reproducible assessment of cellular and physiological responses. Observations from these clinical and preclinical PBM models therefore serve as an essential reference point for interpreting whether, and under what conditions, biologically meaningful effects observed in therapeutic contexts could plausibly translate to lower-intensity, longer-duration environmental IR exposures.

2. Public Health Relevance & Regulatory Context

International standards such as IEC/EN 62471, *Photobiological Safety of Lamps and Lamp Systems*, regulate optical radiation exposure across the 200–3000 nm range by establishing maximum permissible exposure limits to prevent eye and skin injury (IEC, 2006). These standards classify light sources according to wavelength, spectral power distribution, intensity and exposure duration, implicitly acknowledging that light interacts with biological tissue in a wavelength and dose dependent manner. However, their scope is restricted exclusively to the prevention of acute photobiological harm. Unlike nutrients, oxygen or physical activity, light is not addressed within a framework of biological sufficiency. The absence of defined lower exposure thresholds reflects a historical focus on occupational hazard mitigation rather than physiological requirement. Consequently, modern lighting environments are evaluated primarily for their capacity to avoid acute damage, rather than for their potential role in supporting mitochondrial function, vascular and macular health, tissue maintenance or long-term cellular resilience. Modern indoor environments have substantially reduced human exposure to red and NIR radiation, the biologically active wavelengths underpinning PBM, altering the spectral composition of daily light exposure while increasing relative exposure to shorter visible wavelengths such as blue light. The widespread transition to energy efficient light-emitting diode (LED) technologies, many of which are intentionally designed to emit minimal near-infrared radiation, combined with policy-driven restrictions on infrared emissions for efficiency and thermal-management purposes, has further narrowed exposure to biologically relevant wavelengths. In parallel, contemporary architectural features such as coated glazing, low-emissivity glass and predominantly enclosed working environments significantly attenuate infrared transmission from solar and environmental sources, further diminishing ambient red and NIR light exposure. Over the past century, human lifestyles have shifted dramatically toward predominantly indoor living, substantially reducing the time spent outdoors under full-spectrum sunlight. As a result, daily light exposure is now largely derived from artificial indoor lighting, which is typically confined to the visible spectrum and contains little to no red and NIR radiation.

Despite a growing body of mechanistic and experimental evidence indicating that red and NIR wavelengths influence mitochondrial function and broader aspects of biological homeostasis, current regulatory and public-health frameworks do not assess whether chronic underexposure to biologically relevant IR light may have physiological consequences. In particular, potential links to oxidative stress, metabolic dysfunction, impaired tissue repair and reduced cellular resilience remain largely unexplored at the population level. Key research gaps include the absence of epidemiological data characterizing habitual IR exposure, the lack of defined biologically effective exposure ranges, and the limited integration of photobiological principles into environmental and public-health policy. Given the central role of mitochondrial function, redox balance and cellular repair mechanisms in human health, chronic disruption of these processes is associated with a wide range of downstream health outcomes, including cardiometabolic

disorders, neurodegenerative disease, impaired immune function, delayed tissue healing and accelerated biological ageing. Understanding whether reduced exposure to infrared wavelengths contributes to these pathways therefore represents an important and largely unaddressed area of public-health research.

3. Dose Metrics and Parameters

Accurately characterizing biological responses to light requires not only an understanding of wavelength but also of exposure dose. In photobiology, dose reflects the combination of irradiance (power delivered per unit area) and duration of exposure, both of which strongly influence cellular and physiological outcomes. Establishing clear and standardized dose metrics is therefore essential for comparing experimental findings, defining biologically effective exposure ranges and translating photobiological research into practical environmental and public-health guidance.

3.1. Irradiance (Power Density)

Irradiance in PBM refers to the rate at which optical power is delivered to tissue per unit area, typically expressed as milliwatts per square centimetre (mW/cm^2). It is a critical determinant of biological response because it governs the photon flux available for absorption by cellular chromophores, particularly within mitochondria. Evidence from experimental and clinical PBM studies indicates that low to moderate irradiances ($\sim 5\text{--}50 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$) can elicit beneficial cellular effects, including mitochondrial activation, nitric oxide signaling, antioxidant responses and modulation of inflammatory pathways, while remaining below thresholds associated with significant tissue heating (Hamblin, 2017).

3.2. Fluence (Energy Density)

Fluence (J/cm^2), representing total energy delivery over time, is commonly used to describe PBM dose. Effective fluences across biological and clinical studies are frequently reported within approximately $0.1\text{--}25 \text{ J}/\text{cm}^2$, depending on tissue depth and target (Hamblin & Demidova, 2006). However, fluence alone does not predict biological outcome; PBM responses follow a biphasic dose–response in which both insufficient and excessive exposure can limit efficacy. Biological effects therefore depend on the interaction of irradiance, exposure duration and treatment frequency rather than energy dose in isolation (Huang et al., 2011). It is important to acknowledge that the biphasic dose–response framework has not yet been systematically applied to chronic, low-level environmental red and NIR exposures of the kind this paper proposes as a health determinant. Whether typical indoor light environments deliver red and NIR fluences sufficient to cross the threshold for measurable photobiological effect remains an open empirical question. This represents a critical gap in the current evidence base and underscores the need for the scoping review recommended herein, specifically to establish whether environmentally

realistic exposure ranges overlap with biologically effective dose windows, or whether they fall consistently below them.

3.3. Wavelength Considerations

Wavelength selection strongly influences tissue penetration and biological interaction due to wavelength-dependent absorption and scattering in biological tissues. Within the biological optical window (~650–1350 nm), absorption by hemoglobin and water is relatively low and scattering decreases with increasing wavelength, permitting deeper photon propagation compared with visible light (Jacques, 2013). NIR wavelengths commonly used in PBM have therefore been applied to target deeper tissues and engage mitochondrial and vascular signaling pathways, including nitric oxide-mediated effects on endothelial function, through non-thermal mechanisms (Hamblin, 2017). These wavelength-dependent optical properties, together with dose parameters, underpin observed PBM effects and inform translational considerations when evaluating the potential biological relevance of lower-intensity, long-duration environmental NIR exposure.

4. Biological Mechanisms

4.1 Mitochondrial Photoreception and Cellular Energy Metabolism

The foundational mechanism of red and NIR biological activity is photon absorption by mitochondrial chromophores, most notably cytochrome c oxidase (CCO) within the electron transport chain (Karu, 1999; Wong-Riley et al., 2005). Photon absorption leads to enhanced electron transport and oxygen consumption, increased adenosine triphosphate (ATP) synthesis and transient modulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that function as secondary signaling molecules. These mitochondrial effects underpin many of the observed downstream responses to photobiomodulation and represent non-visual photobiological mechanisms (Hamblin, 2017).

4.2 Nitric Oxide Bioavailability and Vascular Signaling

Near-infrared (NIR) light exposure has been shown to increase nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability, thereby modulating endothelial signalling and vascular function (Vladimirov et al., 2004; Lohr et al., 2009). Proposed mechanisms underlying NIR mediated increases in nitric oxide bioavailability include photodissociation of NO from CCO, thereby relieving inhibition of mitochondrial respiration, as well as enhanced phosphorylation and activity of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS). These effects have been reported at wavelengths including 808nm, 1064nm and 1270nm, with biological activity observed at irradiances as low as 10 mW/cm² in endothelial cell models (Yokomizo et al., 2022; Kashiwagi et al., 2023).

4.3 Redox Signaling and Gene Expression

NIR induced stimulation of mitochondrial activity alters cellular redox status, triggering secondary signalling cascades that modulate gene expression. These changes include transcriptional regulation of genes associated with cell proliferation, ATP synthesis (Karu, 1999), ion channel function (Karu et al., 2005), and antioxidant and anti-inflammatory pathways (Hamblin, 2017). For example, NIR mediated increases in reactive oxygen species (ROS) can activate redox-sensitive transcription factors such as NF- κ B, which in turn regulate genes involved in cell survival and stress responses (Chen et al., 2011). NIR exposure has also been shown to influence mitochondrial biogenesis signalling pathways via redox-sensitive regulators; for example, repeated NIR light exposure increased the expression of mitochondrial regulatory proteins such as PGC-1 α in murine skeletal muscle cells (C2C12 myocytes), indicating engagement of mitochondrial gene-regulatory programmes (Nguyen et al., 2014).

4.4 Mitochondrial Melatonin and Antioxidant Defense

Emerging evidence suggests that NIR light may influence intracellular and mitochondrial melatonin dynamics, thereby contributing to enhanced antioxidant defense and cellular stress resilience. Melatonin is now recognized as a ubiquitously synthesized molecule, produced locally in multiple tissues, including immune cells, gastrointestinal tissue and mitochondria, independent of pineal secretion or classical circadian regulation (Tan et al., 2016). Notably, mitochondrial melatonin concentrations are substantially higher than circulating plasma levels, underscoring its primary intracellular and cytoprotective role. Within mitochondria, melatonin exerts multiple protective actions, including scavenging reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, preserving mitochondrial membrane integrity, protecting mitochondrial DNA, and stabilizing electron transport chain function. Unlike classical antioxidants, melatonin exhibits a cascade reaction, whereby its metabolites continue to neutralize reactive species, amplifying its overall antioxidant capacity (Tan et al., 2016). Building on these established properties, Zimmermann and Reiter (2019) proposed that photonic stimulation of mitochondria, particularly via NIR wavelengths, may enhance local melatonin synthesis. Proposed mechanisms include improved electron transport efficiency, redox-sensitive signaling, and upregulation of melatonin-synthesizing enzymes such as arylalkylamine N-acetyltransferase (AANAT) within mitochondria.

It has been proposed that these effects may occur through non-visual, non-circadian pathways, at irradiances below thermal thresholds and independent of retinal photoreception, mediated instead through direct photon absorption by cutaneous and subcutaneous chromophores such as cytochrome c oxidase (Karu, 1999). Recent integrative reviews further expand this conceptual framework by reframing melatonin not solely as a circadian "darkness hormone," but as a fundamental intracellular regulator of redox homeostasis and mitochondrial integrity (Tan et al., 2023). These authors raise the possibility that the deep tissue penetration of NIR radiation may

allow optical signaling to interact with extrapineal and mitochondrial melatonin systems, a biologically plausible mechanistic link between environmental light exposure and cellular antioxidant defense. Taken together, the convergence of photobiology, mitochondrial redox signaling, and melatonin biology offers a mechanistically coherent hypothesis that may help account for the consistent reductions in oxidative stress, inflammation, and tissue damage observed across diverse experimental models of NIR exposure. However, this framework remains incompletely characterized in the context of chronic, low-level environmental exposure and should be regarded as a working hypothesis pending more direct investigation.

4.5 Modulation of Inflammation and Pain

Exposure to NIR light has demonstrated reproducible anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects across both animal and human studies. PBM has been shown to downregulate pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, modulate chronic inflammatory signaling pathways and exert direct neuromodulatory effects on peripheral nociceptive circuits, collectively contributing to reduced pain perception and inflammatory burden (Chung et al., 2011; Hamblin, 2017). These effects are mediated through mitochondrial and redox-dependent mechanisms, including altered nitric oxide signaling and modulation of transcription factors involved in immune activation.

5. Documented Biological Effects

5.1 Macular Degeneration

PBM has demonstrated therapeutic potential in retinal disorders, particularly age-related macular degeneration (AMD), a leading cause of vision loss associated with oxidative stress, inflammation and mitochondrial dysfunction in retinal cells. PBM is proposed to support retinal health by enhancing mitochondrial function, reducing oxidative stress and modulating inflammatory pathways within the retinal pigment epithelium and photoreceptors. Clinical studies using the Valeda Light Delivery System, developed by LumiThera, have reported improvements in visual outcomes in patients with dry AMD. In the LIGHTSITE clinical trials, multiwavelength PBM (590 nm, 660 nm and 850 nm) was associated with improvements in best-corrected visual acuity and other functional visual measures (Boyer et al., 2024). The device has since received authorization from the U.S. Food and Drug Administration for the treatment of dry AMD, representing one of the first regulatory approvals of PBM therapy for a retinal disease.

5.2 Tissue Repair and Regeneration

PBM has been consistently associated with enhanced tissue repair and regenerative processes including accelerated wound closure, improved extracellular matrix organization and enhanced angiogenesis. In a diabetic wound model, PBM increased focal adhesion-mediated migration and proliferation of keratinocytes and fibroblasts, accompanied by elevated collagen, fibronectin,

matrix metalloproteinases, and growth factors such as FGF2 and TGF- β 1, contributing to improved matrix remodeling (Choi *et al.*, 2025). PBM's cellular effects include stimulation of fibroblast proliferation and migration *in vitro*, as well as promotion of keratinocyte wound closure in scratch assay models, demonstrating its capacity to modulate key cellular behaviours involved in tissue repair (Mathioudaki *et al.*, 2024). Systematic reviews further support that PBM modulates gene expression linked to inflammatory cytokines and ECM components (e.g., MMPs), indicating a regulatory influence on the wound-healing genetic programme (Pilar *et al.*, 2024). Clinically, red and near-infrared light therapy has shown particular promise in the management of Diabetic foot ulcers, a complication characterized by impaired healing and high risk of infection and amputation. Randomized clinical studies have reported significantly greater reductions in wound area and faster healing when PBM is used alongside standard care compared with standard treatment alone (Kajagar *et al.*, 2012).

5.3 Pain and Inflammation

A substantial body of preclinical and clinical evidence supports the analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects of PBM across neuropathic, musculoskeletal and inflammatory conditions (Stausholm *et al.*, 2019). Clinical trials and systematic reviews demonstrate that PBM can reduce pain intensity and improve functional outcomes in conditions such as chronic musculoskeletal pain, osteoarthritis and tendinopathies (Bjordal *et al.*, 2006). Preclinical studies consistently show that PBM exposure is associated with reduced inflammatory responses and attenuation of tissue inflammation in experimental injury and disease models (Enwemeka *et al.*, 2004).

5.4 Cardiovascular and Endothelial Function

NIR exposure has been shown in experimental models to increase nitric oxide (NO) bioavailability and influence vascular regulatory pathways (Karu *et al.*, 2005; Hamblin, 2008). Mechanistically, NIR light can induce photodissociation of NO from mitochondrial respiratory chain components, relieving NO-mediated inhibition of electron transport, while also modulating redox-sensitive signaling pathways relevant to vascular tone regulation (Vladimirov *et al.*, 2004). These photobiological effects are associated with enhanced mitochondrial function and altered NO signaling, which together may support microcirculatory regulation and endothelial responsiveness under conditions of oxidative stress or impaired NO availability. While clinical evidence remains limited, preclinical studies indicate that NIR can modulate NO signaling (Yokomizo *et al.*, 2022). Given the role of NO in vascular function, these findings suggest a potential mechanistic link to vascular regulation; however, further human studies are required to establish clinical relevance.

5.5 Nervous System and Brain Function

tPBM, applying red and NIR wavelengths in the 600–1100 nm range at fluences typically between 1–20 J/cm², is under active investigation as a non-invasive approach to neuromodulation, neuroprotection, and attenuation of neuroinflammatory processes (Hamblin, 2016). In transgenic mouse models of Alzheimer's disease, tPBM has been shown to reduce amyloid- β plaque burden and attenuate tau pathology in the cerebral cortex, consistent with proposed neuroprotective mechanisms associated with PBM (Purushothuman et al., 2014). Experimental and mechanistic studies indicate that PBM influences neuronal and glial mitochondrial function by upregulating cytochrome c oxidase activity, enhancing cerebral metabolic activity and ATP production, modulating redox-sensitive signaling pathways, and reducing microglial activation (Rojas & Gonzalez-Lima, 2011; Hamblin, 2017). These effects are associated with reduced neuroinflammation, attenuation of apoptosis, and improvements in neurological function and learning in experimental models of traumatic brain injury, stroke, and neurodegenerative disease (Hamblin, 2018). There is also emerging evidence that PBM may support peripheral nervous system repair; preclinical studies have demonstrated that NIR irradiation promotes nerve regeneration, accelerates axonal regrowth, and reduces demyelination following peripheral nerve injury, suggesting broader utility across the nervous system (Rodrigues et al., 2023). While clinical evidence remains emergent, preclinical findings provide a biologically plausible basis for continued investigation of tPBM as a non-invasive approach to supporting neural resilience and brain health (Cassano et al., 2019).

Conclusion

A substantial body of experimental and early clinical evidence demonstrates that infrared IR and NIR light, when delivered at non-thermal irradiances and appropriate doses, exerts reproducible biological effects across multiple physiological systems. These effects include modulation of mitochondrial energy metabolism, nitric oxide bioavailability, redox-sensitive gene expression, intracellular antioxidant defenses, inflammatory regulation, tissue repair processes, vascular responsiveness and neural function. Importantly, these responses occur through non-visual photobiological pathways and at exposure levels well below established thermal or injury thresholds.

At the population level, this evidence gains particular relevance in the context of modern living environments. Contemporary indoor lifestyles, widespread use of NIR-depleted artificial lighting, architectural attenuation of solar infrared radiation, and increasing time spent in enclosed spaces collectively represent a marked departure from the spectral conditions under which human physiology evolved. This shift has occurred in parallel with rising prevalence of chronic inflammatory conditions, metabolic dysfunction, impaired wound healing, cardiovascular disease, neurodegenerative disorders, and persistent pain, conditions in which mitochondrial dysfunction, oxidative stress, endothelial impairment, and neuroinflammation are

recognized contributors. While causality cannot yet be established, the biological plausibility and consistency of NIR responsive pathways warrant systematic investigation of whether chronic underexposure to biologically relevant infrared wavelengths constitutes an unrecognized environmental risk factor.

Current regulatory frameworks appropriately treat optical radiation as a potential hazard and focus on defining upper exposure limits to prevent acute eye and skin injury. However, this paradigm does not account for biological sufficiency. Other foundational environmental inputs, such as micronutrients, oxygen, physical activity and circadian light exposure, are evaluated not only for toxicity but also for adequacy in supporting physiological function. The successful integration of ultraviolet B exposure into public-health guidance through its relationship with vitamin D synthesis illustrates that optical radiation can be regulated in a manner that balances risk mitigation with biological necessity.

Given the central role of mitochondrial function, redox balance, vascular health, and neuroimmune regulation in population health, the absence of any framework addressing infrared and near-infrared light exposure represents a significant gap. Addressing this gap involves a coordinated research agenda to define typical exposure patterns, establish biologically effective exposure ranges, and evaluate health outcomes in relation to environmental infrared availability.

In this context, infrared and near-infrared light should be recognized as a biologically active component of the human exposome, deserving of the same scientific scrutiny applied to other non-nutritional environmental determinants of health. Incorporating photobiological principles into public-health research and environmental standards would enable a more complete and evidence-based understanding of light not only as a potential hazard, but as a fundamental regulator of human physiology.

Funding and Competing Interests

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